

MARKETING STRATEGY AND ADVERTISEMENT MANAGEMENT IN INDIAN INDUSTRIES

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ABSTRACT

Now it is very well known that since Brands are coming in by dozens, all one needs is the confidence to deliver, to just make it happen- by none other than advertising which forms a vast superstructure with an autonomous existence and an immense influence.

Advertising is one of the most important cultural sign systems that reflect and mould our lives. It is an inevitable part of anyone's life. Even if one does not read the newspaper or watches television it is impossible to escape the advertising images that pervade our surroundings, via hoardings, wall paintings, pop material or even the radio, cutting across all media but limited to none.

Key Words: GDP, CAGR, DAGMAR, AMA.

INTRODUCTION

Advertising and Consumer Behaviour:-

Relationship consumer behaviour is influenced by various factors, ranging from personal motivation, needs attitude and values, personality characteristics, socio-economic and cultural background, age, sex, professional status to social influence of various kinds exerted by family, friend's colleagues and society as a whole. Each person has his / her own standards of judgments and distinct behaviour in every aspects of his/ her role as a consumer. But, at the same time, underlying the individual differences there are similarities which make it possible to explain behaviour of specific types or groups of people. A careful study of consumer behaviour provides the advertiser with deeper insight of his target segments, which in turn proves to be very valuable in strategic advertising decisions, especially in defining the target markets and creating the advertising appeal and message.

The Indian advertising industry has evolved from being a small-scaled business to a full-fledged industry. The advertising industry is projected to be the second fastest growing advertising market in Asia after China. It is estimated that by 2018, the share of ad spend in India's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) will be around 0.45 per cent.

The Indian government has given tremendous support to the advertising and marketing industry. Advertising expenditure is likely to increase in the financial sector, driven by Reserve Bank of India (RBI) policies which could result in a more favourable business environment. Also, proposed licences for new banks and better market sentiments render the advertising and marketing industry in India a fertile space.

1. Market size

Print contributes a significant portion to the total advertising revenue, accounting for almost 41.2 per cent, whereas TV contributes 38.2 per cent, and digital contributes 11 per cent of the total revenue. Outdoor, Radio and Cinema make up the balance 10 per cent.

India's digital advertisement market is expected to grow at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 33.5 per cent to cross the Rs 25,500 crore (US\$ 3.8 billion) mark by 2020.*

The Internet's share in total advertising revenue is anticipated to grow twofold from eight per cent in 2013 to 16 per cent in 2018. Online advertising, which was estimated at Rs 2,900 crore (US\$ 435 million) in 2013, could jump threefold to Rs 10,000 crore (US\$ 1.5 billion) in five years, increasing at a compound annual rate of 28 per cent.

2. Recent Developments:

- GroupM, the US-based advertising media company, has acquired a majority stake in MediaCom India, a joint venture between GroupM India and Madison Media group's principal shareholder Sam Balsara, for an undisclosed amount.
- Dubai-based Iconiction Ltd plans to enter the Indian retail analytics space in partnership with local entrepreneur Mr Anil Hirani, to set up Iconiction India Ltd.

- Flipkart, India's largest e-commerce marketplace has re-entered the private label business by launching Smart Buy, with a view to boost earnings and fill gaps in its product selection.
- Cognizant Technology Solutions has announced the acquisition of Mirabeau BV, a Netherland-based digital marketing and customer experience agency, which is expected to expand Cognizant's capabilities in digital business domain in Netherlands and Europe.
- The Indian Railways is working on a new advertising policy aimed at installing 100,000 big digital screens at 2,175 railway stations across the country, which is expected generate Rs 11,770 crore (US\$ 1.76 billion) revenue annually.
- Times Internet Limited plans to invest US\$ 100 million in development of smart marketing technology platform Colombia, which will serve its marketers to engage with around 200 million digital users per month.
- Zarget, a Software-as-a-Service (SaaS) based conversion rate optimisation start-up, has raised US\$ 1.5 million in seed funding from Accel Partners, Matrix Partners and Freshdesk Inc's founder Mr Girish Mathrubootham, which will be used to build more marketing related tools.
- Snapdeal.com, one of India's largest and fast growing e-commerce companies, has acquired TargetingMantra (Insightful Pvt. Ltd), which is a Gurugram-based marketing and personalisation services company, as part of its plan to enhance the experience for its customers.
- Indian Railways has appointed Ernst & Young (EY) as a consultant to discover its advertising potential, which is in line with the Railway Budget proposal of increasing non-fare earnings to over Rs 5,000 crore (US\$ 750 million) in five years.
- MoMark Services, a mobile based customer engagement platform for small and medium businesses, has raised US\$ 600,000 from YourNest Angel Fund and LNB Group, to scale up its product offerings and talent acquisition.
- Tata Motors has appointed renowned football player Lionel Messi as the global brand ambassador for Tata cars and utility vehicles globally, with an aim to tap the youth market and expand visibility and presence of Tata Motors in newer markets.
- Advertising agency J Walter Thompson has launched its global digital agency network 'Mirum' in India which will provide services such as strategy and consulting services,

campaigns and content, experience and platforms, analytics and innovation and product development, with the target to increase non-traditional media revenues to 40-45 per cent from 35 per cent currently.

- DDB Mudra Group has planned to launch 'Track DDB', a brand that addresses the data-led world of marketing communications, which will provide services like creative, data and digital analytics, database marketing, CRM, digital and mobile marketing in India.
- All India Radio (AIR) has appointed 'releaseMyAd' as a virtual agency to let advertisers book ads for all of AIR's station online.
- Google is all set to help India implement Prime Minister Mr Narendra Modi's "Digital India" initiative, and the government has a well laid out plan to realise it, said Google's Chief Internet Evangelist Mr Vinton G. Cerf. Digital India is Rs 1.13 trillion (US\$ 16.95 billion) government initiative that seeks to transform the country into a connected economy, attract investment in electronics manufacturing, and create millions of jobs and support trade.
- As companies look for better productivity and increasing efficiencies in a tough market environment, market research firm Nielsen has launched its first consumer neuroscience lab in India at its Mumbai headquarters. The neuroscience lab will augment the company's research capabilities in packaging and research, improving their effectiveness.
- MPS North America LLC, the US subsidiary of Bengaluru-based publishing solutions provider MPS Ltd, has acquired Electronic Publishing Services Inc. (EPS), a New York-based firm with interests in content creation, art rendering, design and production. The deal will allow MPS to strengthen its foothold in North America.
- Jaipur-based Girnar Software Private Limited, which owns and operates the website CarDekho.com, announced that it has raised US\$ 50 million in its second round of funding. The funding was led by Hillhouse Capital with participation from Tybourne Capital and Sequoia Capital.
- ZipDial has become the first Indian technology product startup to be bought by Twitter in what is the third such deal led by a global corporation following the acquisitions by Facebook and Yahoo. The ZipDial deal is expected to cost Twitter US\$ 34-35 million.

This feature is expected to help Twitter reach people who will come online for the first time in countries such as Brazil, India and Indonesia, mostly using a mobile device.

- Telecom major Axiata's subsidiary, Axiata Digital Advertising (ADA) has formed a joint venture with US-based advertising tech firm Adknowledge to get into the US\$ 47 billion digital ad market in the Asia Pacific region and has identified India as a 'key' market.

3. GOVERNMENT INITIATIVES

The Governments of India and Canada have signed an audio-visual co-production deal which facilitates producers from both countries to harness their collective artistic, technical, financial and marketing resources, and encourage exchange of culture and art between the two countries. The agreement is also likely to lead to better promotion of Indian locales for shooting films. "The agreement will also lead to the transparent funding of film production and boost export of Indian films into the Canadian market," as per the agreement.

India and Poland are seeking to enhance cooperation in the digitisation and restoration of film archives. This was decided in a meeting between Mr Bimal Julka, Secretary of Information and Broadcasting, India, and a delegation from Poland led by Ms Malgorzata Omilanowska, Secretary of State. The two countries will form a joint working group that will help improve cooperation in fields such as student exchange programmes, animation, films and digitisation, among others. Mr Rajyavardhan Singh Rathore, Minister of State for Information & Broadcasting, has announced that Indian government has planned to increase advertising spend on the digital platform which will help increase the government's presence in digital media.

How dose Advertising affects consumers-

Advertising, along with a number of other factors viz price, distribution, sales force, packaging, product features, competitive actions and changing buyer needs and tasters influence sales isolating the effects of advertising is extremely difficult. Advertising might attract buyers who will be loyal customers for many years to come or might start the development of positive attitudes or brand equity that will culminate in purchase much later. Advertising influences consumer and his decision making in a number of ways. It not only educated him about his problems or needs, provides required information and assists him in

comparing the various alternatives and arriving at final decision. As it is a cyclical process, it also has impact over the post purchase behavior of the consumer. Often, the consumers are either not aware of their needs or are confused about their problems. To them, advertising provides clues; therefore advertising provides the consumer motives to purchase the advertised product. As in the present scenario the strategy is to keep on changing or improving the product. As in the present scenario the strategy is to keep on changing or improving the product or its features, it becomes imperative to inform the consumers about the minor innovations and the way it can solve their problems – the problems which the consumers feel and is at the surface or the problems which had not captured the attention of the consumers. Advertising also provides the necessary support after the consumer has made the purchase. If the consumers experience dissonance or discomforts Moving to their purchase decision, then advertisement reduce this feeling of discomfort by providing information on the products attributes. It is even more necessary to neutralize the impact of the advertisements of rival brands. Keeping the above facts in view an attempt has been made to find out whether advertising has an impact on brand awareness and preference on men's garment in the study area of Navi Mumbai, has also experienced the shift in men's shopping pattern and methodology used as the city witnesses significant economic, demographic, social cultural development. People of this city are customizing themselves to the fashion revolution and men are a major contributing factor and greatly affected by the same as well. New avenues are reshaping and redirecting the general marketing/shopping culture prevalent.

Advertising helps to make consumers aware of a product and aims to build preference for that product over its competitors. If advertising succeeds in those two tasks, consumers will choose the advertised product when they make their next purchase. However, building awareness and preference through advertising is a cumulative process. A single campaign only raises awareness for a short period, so it is important to allocate the budget for advertising over a period of time to sustain high levels of awareness and use.

4. Choices

When consumers make choices between different products or brands, two conditions apply, according to C.R. Clark of the Institute of Applied Economics, writing in the journal

"Quantitative Marketing and Economics." The product must form part of a consumer's set of choices and the consumer must prefer one product over all others in the set of choices. If market research indicates that a consumer is aware of products A, B and C and you supply product X, you must make consumers aware of your product so that it becomes part of their set of choices.

5. Preference

By advertising, you can make consumers aware of the existence and availability of your product. However, raising awareness is only the first stage in persuading consumers to buy and use your product. Your advertising must convince them of the quality of the product. Including testimonials from satisfied customers or reporting achievement of quality standards in your advertisements helps to build confidence and preference for your product.

6. Time

Awareness and preference increase or decrease over time, depending on the weight and frequency of advertising, according to David W. Olson in an article for "Advances in Consumer Research." Frequent advertising can build the level of awareness from recognition of some elements of a product through to detailed understanding of the nature of the product and its benefits. Levels of awareness and preference can decline if you do not continue to advertise or if competitors increase their weight of advertising compared to yours.

7. Interactive

Advertising on the Internet makes it easier to measure the effects of advertising on product awareness and use, according to Paul A. Pavlou and David W. Stewart in the "Journal of Interactive Advertising." When consumers click on your Internet advertisement to obtain further product information, you can immediately measure the success of a campaign in terms of the number of responses. If consumers then purchase the advertised product online, you have a direct measure of campaign effectiveness on product use.

8. Mix

Although you can use advertising to raise product awareness and use, you must also take into account the other methods consumers use to obtain product information. Consumers collect and share information by searching or posting reviews and feedback on websites. They also exchange

information and preferences through social networking sites, influencing other consumers' choices in a way similar to traditional advertising.

Consumer preferences towards brand indicate the following:-

9. **Brand Unawareness-** A buyer has no knowledge of the existence of the brand.
Brand Awareness- A buyer is aware of the existence of the brand but the knowledge about it is limited and obviously has no particular emotional attachment to it as a result he may or may not think of purchasing the brand.
10. **Brand Acceptance-** A buyer can buy the brand as he has no negative feeling about the brand but he has open mind to try another brand.
11. **Brand Preference-** The buyer favours a particular Brand but he can think for other brand which is next in his preference schedule.
12. **Brand Loyalty-**The attachment towards a particular Brand is very strong and if the brand is unavailable, only then, he can think of buying another brand.
13. **Brand Insistence-** A buyer insists on purchasing and one brand only and will not at all accept a substitute.
14. **Brand Equity-** In the 80s much of the growth of the giant consumer product corporation was achieved by a strategy of acquiring valuable brand names from other companies, often the price paid for such transaction is huge. This is quite obvious that brand names that are well known and wee liked by the consumer have greater equity hence are worth more, David Aaker feels (4). Brands have equity because they have high awareness, many loyal consumers, a high reputation for perceived quality.

NEED FOR THE STUDY

As a study it shows the role of advertising which is absolutely essential to connect with the consumers. To sustain themselves in the minds of the target consumers, to make sure they don't shift their loyalty from one product/service to another. In a bid to outdo one another they even offer lower and lower rates with every need of the consumer being satisfied.

Promotional offers being splashed across advertising campaigns have become the order of the day. Advertising plays a key role in influencing the consumer's decision in continuing the product/Service provider or switching to another product/service provider. No one can deny the omnipresent status of advertising keeping the consumers abreast of latest offers and schemes.

This study is for specific strategies used by two-wheeler companies for their brand building exercise on their targeted audience.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Review of literature shows the previous studies carried out by the researcher in this field. Previous studies are reviewed in order to gain insight into extent of research. The research problem can be more understood and made specific referring to theories, reports, records and other information made in similar studies. This will provide the researcher with the knowledge on what lines the study should proceed and serves to narrow the problem. The main objective of the study is to measure Brand Awareness of TNPL products among the people and the reviews are as follows:

Brand:

A traditional definition of a brand was: "the name associated with one or more items in the product line, that is used to identify the source of character of the item(s)"(Kotler, 2000).

The American Marketing Association (AMA) definition of a brand is "a name, term, sign, symbol, or design, or a combination of them, intended to identify the goods and services of one seller or group of sellers and to differentiate them from those of competitors"

Percy and Rossiter (1992) argue that the two types of awareness, namely *brand recall* and *brand recognition*, operate in fundamentally different ways in the purchase decision. For routine purchases such as fast moving consumer goods (FMCG), few shoppers carry shopping lists. For them, the presentation of brands at the point-of-sale acts as a visual reminder and triggers category need. In this case, brand recognition is the dominant mode of awareness. For other purchases, where the brand is not present, the consumer first experiences category need then searches memory for brands within that category. Many services, such as home help, gardening services, pizza delivery fall into this category. In this case, the category need precedes brand

awareness. Such purchases are recall dominant, and the consumer is more likely to select one of the brands elicited from memory. When brand recall is dominant, it is not necessary for consumers to like the advertisement, but they must like the brand. In contrast, consumers should like the ad when brand recognition is the communications objective.

The distinction between *brand recall* and *brand recognition* has important implications for advertising strategy. When the communications objectives depend on *brand recognition*, the creative execution must show the brand packaging or a recognisable brand name. However, when the communications objectives rely on *brand recall*, the creative execution should encourage strong associations between the category and the brand. Advertisers also use jingles, mnemonics and other devices to encourage brand recall.

Brand dominance occurs when, during brand recall tests, most consumers can name only one brand from a given category. Brand dominance is defined as an individual's selection of only certain brand names in a related category during brand recall procedure. While brand dominance might appear to be a desirable goal, overall dominance can be a double-edged sword.

15. Brand awareness and the hierarchy of effects

Brand awareness is a standard feature of a group of models known as hierarchy of effects models. Hierarchical models are linear sequential models built on an assumption that consumers move through a series of cognitive and affective stages, beginning with brand awareness (or category awareness) and culminating in the purchase decision. In these models, advertising and marketing communications operate as an external stimulus and the purchase decision is a consumer response.

A number of hierarchical models can be found in the literature including DAGMAR and AIDA. In a survey of more than 250 papers, Vakratsas and Ambler (1999) found little empirical support for any of the hierarchies of effects. In spite of that, some authors have argued that hierarchical models continue to dominate theory, especially in the area of marketing communications and advertising.

The hierarchy of effects developed by Lavidge in the 1960s is one of the original hierarchical models. It proposes that customers progress through a sequence of six stages from brand awareness through to the purchase of a product.

Stage 1: Awareness - The consumer becomes aware of a category, product or brand (usually through advertising)

Stage 2: Knowledge - The consumer learns about the brand (e.g. sizes, colours, prices, availability etc.)

Stage 3: Liking - The consumer develops a favourable/unfavourable disposition towards the brand.

Stage 4: Preference - The consumer begins to rate one brand above other comparable brands.

Stage 5: Conviction - The consumer demonstrates a desire to purchase (via inspection, sampling, trial)

Stage 6: Purchase - The consumer acquires the product.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- 1) To study the Automobile industry scenario in India.
- 2) To evaluate the need for strong advertising back-up for creating awareness of the product providers among the masses.
- 3) To understand the life-cycle of product providers from inception to its present status.

- 4) To elaborate the advertising strategies to combat competition between close competitors.
- 5) To briefly describe, the consumers' perspective, the impact of the brand building exercise on its targeted audience.
- 6) To suggest future advertising trends for the two wheeler service providers.

CONCLUSION

With the dawning of complexities due to product and brand proliferation, excessive communication, attempts to create real and artificial differentiation and claiming and counter – claiming at the point of purchase leaves the buyer nothing but confused and frustrated. Negotiating this highly complex buying environment is a new emerging phenomenon of the post industrialized world. The excess of supply over demand has made the life of marketers miserable. The pressures to improve the bottom line and top line are causing the marketers to pull and deploy all kinds of ammunitions from their arsenals. In this context, brands and branding have assumed new significance. In branding the marketing sees salvation. On the one hand, brands have emerged as new trusted compasses that help consumers spot the correct way through the dense and dangerous marketing jungle. Brand is the consumer's formula to handle buying – an essential task or enjoyable task for survival. Brands are there because we want them. We may not expressly articulate the need for brands and even criticize them and call them 'manipulative' and in some cases 'exploitative'. But the fact is that we need them. That's what marketers know. Therefore, brands are created.

It also describes the consumers perspective's at being inundated with so many offers, each more competitive than the other. It voices the opinions of consumers at the clutter of advertisements each service provider is churning out to become a market leader.

The study traces and details the brand from the consumer's point of view from a cross section of consumers. What the brand was, it's changing face and how it is perceived as of today. The study focuses on the following aspects:

- a) Target Audience.

- b) Market segmentation.
- c) Media Selection.
- d) Image of the brand in the consumer's mind.
- e) Positioning of the brand as against the other brands in the market.

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